

From Dice to Metaverses: Gamifying Musical Experiences

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Abstract

This paper provides a historical survey of gamification concepts and techniques applied to music composition, performance, and listening experiences. It traces the origins back to 18th century musical dice games before exploring how digital technology enabled new interactive and immersive possibilities pioneered by composers like Xenakis, Tudor, and Laurie Anderson. The growth of gamified musical experiences is highlighted, both experimental works in virtual worlds/metaverses as well as mainstream concerts like Travis Scott's Fortnite event. Psychological concepts like flow state are discussed in relation to fostering creativity and engagement through game-like elements. Recent examples are also examined, such as Enrique Tomas' Ars Electronica's Metaverse and Ecstasy / Light / Inertia. This paper positions current musical gamification practices within a rich historical tradition.

CCS Concepts

• **Applied computing** → **Sound and music computing**; Media arts; • **Software and its engineering** → *Interactive games*.

Keywords

gamification, musical dice games, interactive music, immersive experiences, virtual worlds, metaverse, flow state, COVID-19 pandemic, user engagement, game design

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1 The Analog Era

While the term "gamification" is more commonly associated with digital games and experiences, the practice of introducing playful, game-like elements into music creation and listening can be traced back well before the advent of modern technology. Some of the earliest examples emerge in the 18th century, when a fascinating trend of "musical dice games" allowed composers to create new works through systematic chance operations and combinatorial techniques.

Between 1757 and 1812, at least 20 different musical dice games were composed and published, each providing a framework for any person to effectively generate new pieces by throwing dice to select and arrange pre-composed musical fragments [19]. The first of these pioneering works was Johann Philipp Kirnberger's *Der allezeit fertige Menuetten- und Polonaisencomponist* (The Ever-Ready Minuet and Polonaise Composer) from 1757 [25].

Kirnberger's game included numerical tables corresponding to different dance forms, where a dice roll would direct the player to specific measure-level musical cells notated on cards to be assembled into a complete composition [19].

Perhaps the most famous example from this era is the *Musikalisches Würfelspiel* K. 516f (Musical Dice Game), a pamphlet published in 1792 and attributed to Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart, though his authorship has been debated [40]. As seen in Figure 1, an early 1793 edition from publisher N. Simrock explains how throwing dice determines the selection of one of 11 different musical ideas for each of the 16 bars, allowing the user to stochastically construct around 45.9 quadrillion possible waltzes [16]. Despite the controversy over Mozart's direct involvement, this dice game has inspired numerous re-interpretations, analyses, and computer realizations over the centuries [4].

ZAHLENTAFEL.
TABLE de CHIFFRES.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
2	96	92	141	41	106	192	11	30
3	24	67	128	62	140	46	124	81
4	89	95	168	39	143	54	120	24
5	40	17	113	84	161	9	169	100
6	148	74	163	45	80	97	36	107
7	104	147	97	167	144	64	118	91
8	149	60	171	49	99	133	91	197
9	119	54	114	40	140	86	169	34
10	98	142	48	146	75	129	69	193
11	3	87	164	61	134	47	147	38
12	24	120	10	109	94	37	106	4

Erster Theil.
Premiere Partie.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
2	70	121	96	9	112	49	109	14
3	117	39	126	66	174	18	116	88
4	66	129	14	129	73	38	144	79
5	90	176	7	34	67	160	39	170
6	146	143	64	144	76	136	1	93
7	128	71	140	99	101	162	23	141
8	16	144	47	174	43	168	80	179
9	140	84	44	166	41	114	72	111
10	64	77	19	82	127	28	142	8
11	102	4	31	104	144	49	173	78
12	34	40	108	92	12	124	44	121

Zweiter Theil.
Seconde Partie.

Figure 1: Score of Mozart's Dice Game, published in Bonn by N. Simrock (1793)

A more elaborate example is found in Professor J. Clinton's *The Quadrille Melodist* from 1865, consisting of a box of cards with

musical fragments that could be shuffled, reorganized, and placed into a special tray with slots for sequential playback (see Figure 2) [14]. Each bar had 11 possible variations, theoretically allowing over 7.4 sextillion unique combinations, though the original publication claimed a more modest 428 million [6]. Two different card sets were provided to generate distinct dances.

Figure 2: The tray with cards placed on corresponding slots from *The Quadrille Melodist* (British Library)

Musicologist Leonard Meyer suggests the 19th century saw a decline in such games, attributed to a paradigm shift that prioritized coherent thematic development and authentic self-expression over chance-based processes [24]. Nonetheless, these early examples demonstrate a clear historical impulse to infuse playfulness, interactivity, and an element of chance into musical experiences, foreshadowing many later developments in the 20th century and beyond.

Evidently, the explosion of diverse aesthetic trends in the 20th and 21st centuries provided fertile ground for composers to create sonic pieces infused with various game-like elements. Some incorporated more subtle ludic influences, such as David Tudor's *Rainforest IV* (1973). This work invited audiences to explore and interact with a metaphorical forest of resonating sculptural objects activated by performers in an informal, curiosity-piquing setting (see Figure 3) [8, 36]. Tudor aimed to highlight the "acoustically transformative properties" of the objects, describing it as bringing together multiple "natures" in a game-like spirit [29]. He was fond of encouraging children to playfully engage with the sculptures [13].

Game influences manifested in the very sounds themselves, as composer John Driscoll incorporated amplified video game audio as source material [29]. This multi-layered gamification extended to Driscoll's background in professional game design [32].

2 Transition Towards the Digital Age

The increasing sophistication of digital interfaces catalyzed new possibilities for interactive, gamified musical experiences. Iannis Xenakis' UPIC system exemplifies this paradigm shift. The acronym refers to the *Unité Polyagogique Informatique du CEMAMu*, a

Figure 3: Children biting a sculpture, ICA, Philadelphia, 1979 (Photo © Kira Perov)

drawing tablet interface that could translate graphic inputs into sound (see Figure 4) [22]. In a 1979 interview, Xenakis likened UPIC to a game, allowing unfettered imagination and composition without the prerequisites of music theory or an instrument [39]. He frequently highlighted how familiar children were with such digital creative tools [9, 42].

Figure 4: UPIC system setup (© CIX Archives)

Xenakis' characterization aligns with the psychological theory of flow, describing an intrinsically motivating state of intense focus and creative engagement [11]. Achieving a flow state is a common goal in game design, and its association with unlocking creativity supports Xenakis' framing of UPIC as a gamelike musical vehicle [20, 37].

The rise of digital interfaces and technologies allowing more direct interaction with virtual worlds marked a crucial transition point for gamification. This increasing accessibility to interactive

experiences cemented the term's modern association with digital media, though its artistic roots ran deeper [15]. One pioneering work embodying this shift was American composer David Behrman's body of interactive multimedia pieces from the 1980s and early 90s. Works like *Sound Fountain* (1982), *Mbirascope*, *A Map of the Known World* (1986-7), and *Keys to Your Music* (1989) incorporated clear game-like qualities of exploration, progression, and audience engagement aided by computer graphics [5]. As seen in Figure 5, *Sound Fountain* featured gamified digital representations of percussive characters controlled by guitar-like interfaces, inviting children's playful participation at the Hudson River Museum.

Figure 5: Children interacting with the Sound Fountain installation at the Hudson River Museum

Behrman directly linked the graphic components to cultivating a sense of ludic progression and encouraging exploratory impulses central to game design principles [3, 30]. This fusion of visual, interactive, and sonic elements exemplified the expanded artistic possibilities as powerful home computers and gaming consoles proliferated in the late 1980s. The technological capabilities required for sound-centered, fully virtual, gamified musical experiences were not realized until affordable analog-to-digital and digital-to-analog converters became available for multimedia personal computers in the early 1990s [28]. This "heralded a new era" allowing uninhibited experimentation at the intersection of sound, graphics, and code [31]. Immersive interactive artworks could now reside entirely within digital three-dimensional realms.

One landmark example from this period is Laurie Anderson's *Puppet Motel* CD-ROM from 1995, built around principles of non-linear storytelling and open-ended virtual exploration very much akin to a video game experience. Users could freely navigate a series of distinct interconnected "rooms," each containing self-contained narratives, sonic environments, and interactive opportunities, accessed via a central hub space (Figure 6).

Anderson's work was undoubtedly a pioneering artistic gamification of virtual musical experiences, forging an influential path for future immersive experiments blurring boundaries between games, installations, and performance.

Figure 6: The Hall of Time hub area in Laurie Anderson's Puppet Motel

3 Modern Applications

Since around 2010, gamification has seen rapidly growing interest and implementation across private and academic sectors [18]. Studies demonstrate its positive impacts on engagement, motivation, and enjoyment when applied to fields like education [10, 12], health [21], innovation [38], workplace activities [26], and marketing/customer relations [41].

Music has also experienced a proliferation of gamified works and experiences: A notable early example was Pauline Oliveros' *Rotating Brains / Beating Heart* from 2010, an interactive remote performance inside the virtual world *Second Life* featuring audio triggered by 3D avatar movements and choreography (Figure 7) [1].

Figure 7: Rotating Brains / Beating Heart by Pauline Oliveros

This pioneered a wave of gamified virtual reality operas and musical pieces like *She* (2017), *Croak* (2018) [17], the upcoming *Climb!VR*, and Matthew Burtner's *Dwelling in the Enfolding Glaciers* (2020) [7]. Game controllers have even been repurposed as musical interfaces, such as in Joo Won Park's *PS Quartet* compositions [27].

The COVID-19 pandemic provided further motivation, as physical distancing necessitated digital alternatives for music dissemination. Sound artist Enrique Tomas presented a gamified multiplayer metaverse at *Ars Electronica 2020* featuring interactive sonic artworks and virtual performances [2, 34]. The 2020 Lumen Prize and

the Society for Electro-Acoustic Music in the United States (SEAMUS) National Conference 2021 created similar gamified virtual exhibition spaces. Mainstream musicians like Travis Scott embraced game engines too, staging the record-breaking Astronomical concert inside Fortnite attended by over 27 million players [33]. This demonstrated how free-to-play games can enable democratized access to large-scale immersive musical experiences [23].

A notable recent example of gamified musical experiences is *Ecstasy / Light / Inertia*, released in 2023 [35]. This interactive narrative-driven application proposes a novel method for experiencing new music in a gamified setting, integrating high-fidelity spatial audio compositions into a sophisticated 3D environment built using Unreal Engine. The work combines elements of Nordic nature, modernist architecture, and philosophical narratives, offering a multifaceted experience that transcends traditional concert settings or sound art galleries.

Available on Steam and featured in the "Future Archives: Interaction of Technology, Art, Games and Algorithms" exhibition at the Hanshan Art Museum in China, *Ecstasy / Light / Inertia* demonstrates the potential for music-centric video games to bridge commercial and artistic spheres. The project utilizes advanced audio technologies like NVIDIA VRWorks Audio for realistic sound propagation, and incorporates narrative-driven design to guide users through its virtual spaces. By offering alternative endings based on player choices, the work encourages active engagement with its themes of memory, identity, and sacrifice, representing an innovative approach to designing, disseminating, and experiencing musical artworks in the digital age (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Screenshot of *Ecstasy / Light / Inertia*

4 Conclusions

The examples highlighted throughout this survey illustrate the profound potential for gamification to reshape and revitalize practices of musical creation, performance, and listening. As technological capabilities rapidly evolve, the further integration of game-like elements seems poised to open new frontiers for sonic expression and audience engagement.

From the seminal combinatorial "musical dice games" of the 18th century to the latest genre-defying immersive virtual reality environments, a core impulse to instill playfulness, agency, and ludic frameworks into musical experiences has persisted across eras

and artistic movements. Gamified approaches have demonstrated the ability to unlock creativity, foster flow states of heightened focus, and make transformative sonic artworks more accessible to wider audiences. With technological capabilities rapidly evolving, further integration of game-like elements seems poised to open new frontiers for sonic expression and audience engagement.

This comprehensive survey provides a unique historical perspective on the evolution of gamification in music, illuminating a consistent thread of innovation that has enhanced musical engagement through ludic elements. By synthesizing disparate examples into a coherent narrative, we highlight the enduring relevance of gamification principles in music and provide a foundation for future research. This historical context is crucial for understanding current trends and anticipating future directions in the field, such as the impact of emerging technologies, the role of gamified music in education, and its potential to address issues of inclusivity and democratization in musical experiences.

As we look to the future, the intersection of music and gamification continues to present exciting possibilities. The ongoing evolution of virtual and augmented reality technologies, artificial intelligence, and interactive platforms promises to further expand the horizons of musical gamification. By understanding the historical trajectory and current state of this field, we are better equipped to harness its potential for creating more engaging, accessible, and innovative musical experiences in the years to come.

References

- [1] [n. d.]. Rotating Brains Beating Heart, YouTube video showcase. <https://youtube/AzwYogTMw24>. Accessed: 2020-11-16.
- [2] 2020. Personal communication with Enrique Tomas. E-mail communication.
- [3] Ernest Adams and Joris Dormans. 2012. *Game mechanics: advanced game design*. New Riders.
- [4] Christopher Ariza. 2011. Two pioneering projects from the early history of computer-aided algorithmic composition. *Computer Music Journal* 35, 3 (2011), 40–56.
- [5] David Behrman. 1991. Designing interactive computer-based music installations. *Contemporary Music Review* 6, 1 (1991), 139–142.
- [6] Nikita Braguinski. 2019. "428 Millions of Quadrilles for 5s. 6d.": John Clinton's Combinatorial Music Machine. *19th-Century Music* 43, 2 (2019), 86–98.
- [7] Matthew Burtner. [n. d.]. EcoSono - Dwelling in the Enfolding. <http://www.ecosono.org/portfoliodwelling-in-the-enfolding/>. Accessed: 2021-04-30.
- [8] Laura Cameron and Matt Rogalsky. 2006. Conserving Rainforest 4: aural geographies and ephemerality. *Social & Cultural Geography* 7, 6 (2006), 909–926.
- [9] Joel Chadabe. 1997. *Electric sound: the past and promise of electronic music*. Pearson.
- [10] Christopher Cheong, France Cheong, and Justin Filippou. 2013. Quick Quiz: A Gamified Approach for Enhancing Learning. In *Pacis*. Jeju Island, 206.
- [11] Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi, Sami Abuhumdeh, and Jeanne Nakamura. 2014. Flow. In *Flow and the foundations of positive psychology*. Springer, 227–238.
- [12] Paul Denny, Fiona McDonald, Ruth Empson, Philip Kelly, and Andrew Petersen. 2018. Empirical support for a causal relationship between gamification and learning outcomes. In *Proceedings of the 2018 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. 1–13.
- [13] John Driscoll and Matt Rogalsky. 2004. David Tudor's rainforest: an evolving exploration of resonance. *Leonardo Music Journal* (2004), 25–30.
- [14] Michael Edwards. 2011. Algorithmic composition: computational thinking in music. *Commun. ACM* 54, 7 (2011), 58–67.
- [15] Mathias Fuchs. 2014. Predigital precursors of gamification. (2014).
- [16] Martin Gardner. 1970. Mathematical games. *Scientific american* 222, 6 (1970), 132–140.
- [17] Hans-Peter Gasselseder and Maria Kallionpää. 2019. Beyond the Audience Seat: The recording and production of immersive opera and interactive concerto programmes for VR experiences. *Proceedings of EVA London 2019* (2019), 409–416.
- [18] Juho Hamari, Jonna Koivisto, and Harri Sarsa. 2014. Does gamification work?—a literature review of empirical studies on gamification. In *2014 47th Hawaii international conference on system sciences*. Ieee, 3025–3034.
- [19] Stephen A Hedges. 1978. Dice music in the eighteenth century. *Music & Letters* 59, 2 (1978), 180–187.

- [20] Marius Kalinauskas et al. 2014. Gamification in fostering creativity. *Socialinės Technologijos* 4, 01 (2014), 62–75.
- [21] Jonna Koivisto and Juho Hamari. 2019. Gamification of physical activity: A systematic literature review of comparison studies. In *3rd International GamiFIN Conference, GamiFIN 2019*. CEUR-WS.
- [22] Henning Lohner. 1986. the UPIC system: A User's Report. *Computer Music Journal* 10, 4 (1986), 42–49.
- [23] Hei Wan Mak, Meg Fluharty, and Daisy Fancourt. 2020. Predictors and impact of arts engagement during the COVID-19 pandemic: analyses of data from 19,384 adults in the COVID-19 Social Study. (2020).
- [24] Leonard B Meyer. 1996. *Style and music: Theory, history, and ideology*. University of Chicago Press.
- [25] Gerhard Nierhaus. 2009. *Algorithmic composition: paradigms of automated music generation*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- [26] Florin Oprea, Christian Jones, and Mary Katsikitis. 2014. IPLAY AT WORK—ten principles for transforming work processes through gamification. *Frontiers in psychology* 5 (2014), 14.
- [27] Joo Won Park. 2018. Analysis of DualShock 4 as a Musical Instrument. 16 (2018), 51–57.
- [28] Curtis Roads, John Strawn, et al. 1996. *The computer music tutorial*. MIT press. 13 pages.
- [29] Matthew R Rogalsky. 2006. *Idea and community: the growth of David Tudor's Rainforest, 1965-2006*. Ph. D. Dissertation. City University London.
- [30] Richard Rouse III. 2004. *Game design: Theory and practice*. Jones & Bartlett Publishers.
- [31] David Salomon. 2011. *The computer graphics manual*. Springer Science & Business Media. 5 pages.
- [32] Travis Scott. [n. d.]. Travis Scott and Fortnite Present: Astronomical - Youtube Video. <https://youtu.be/wYeFAIVC8qU>. Accessed: 2020-12-02.
- [33] Dave Thier. [n. d.]. A Staggering Number Of People Saw Fortnite's Travis Scott 'Astronomical' Event - Forbes' article. Apr 28, 2020. Accessed: 2020-11-18.
- [34] Enrique Tomas. 2020. *Personal Communication*.
- [35] Juan Carlos Vasquez Gomez. 2022. Interactive Gamification for New Experimental Music: Initial Findings. In *Extended Abstracts of the 2022 Annual Symposium on Computer-Human Interaction in Play*. 103–106.
- [36] Bill Viola. 2004. David Tudor: The Delicate Art of Falling. *Leonardo Music Journal* (2004), 49–56.
- [37] Carolyn Wagner. 2017. Digital gamification in private music education. *Antistasis* 7, 1 (2017).
- [38] Maximilian Witt, Christian W Scheiner, and Susanne Robra-Bissantz. 2011. Gamification of online idea competitions: insights from an explorative case.. In *GI-Jahrestagung*. Citeseer, 392.
- [39] Iannis Xenakis. 1980. Si Dieu existait, il serait bricoleur. *Les Entretien du Monde de la musique* (1980), 93–97.
- [40] Neal Zaslaw. 2005. *Mozart's Modular Minuet Machine*. na.
- [41] Gabe Zichermann and Christopher Cunningham. 2011. *Gamification by design: Implementing game mechanics in web and mobile apps*. " O'Reilly Media, Inc'.
- [42] Sharon Kanach) ZKM | Hertz-Labor (Peter Weibel, Ludger Brümmer. 2020. From Xenakis's UPIC to Graphic Notation Today. (2020).